

2016 JOINT CHAPTER MEETING CAA NL/FL & CAA DE, NOVEMBER 24-25, 2016: PRELIMINARY PROGRAMME

November 24th, 2016

08:30 – 09:15 Registration

09:15 – 09:30 Welcome

09:30 – 11:00 Session 1: Statistical Analysis / Network Analysis in Archaeology

- **Schmidt, Sophie C.:** What happens if... Inter-site Settlement Analysis Based on Features.
- **Donnellan, Lieve:** The elusive character of social interaction in archaeological networks.
- **Groenhuizen, Mark:** Comparison of different network construction techniques to model the distribution of rural surplus production in the Dutch limes zone.

11:00 – 11:30 Coffee Break

11:30 – 13:00 Session 1: Statistical Analysis / Network Analysis in Archaeology

- **Da Vela, Raffaella:** Two-mode or One-Mode Networks? How to analyse relationships based on the tie of the material culture.
- **Roth, Georg:** The Egg of Columbus? Evaluating t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding as archaeological Ordination/Clustering Method.
- **Deicke, Aline:** Exploring the potential of graph databases for network research through the analysis of clustering in bipartite graphs.

13:00 – 14:00 Lunch

14:00 – 15:30 Session 2: Archival and Management of (3D) Archaeological Data

- **Meyer, Jessica N.:** Volumetric measurements as a quality control tool for archaeological data.
- **Göbel, Karin:** Modular System for big GIS-projects.
- **De Hond, Rens:** 3D technologies along the Via Appia – Issues and solutions.

15:30 – 16:00 Coffee Break

16:00 – 17:00 Session 2: Archival and Management of (3D) Archaeological Data

- **Trognitz, Martina:** Archiving 3D Data: Formats, Metadata and What is Missing.
- **Kaminski, Steve; Gieseler, Jens; Lang, Matthias:** Archiving Archaeological Data-Sets in the Tübingen Archive-System.

17:00 – 17:10 Announcement SIG - Standards in Digital Archaeology

17:10 Reception

November 25th, 2016

08:30 – 09:00 Registration

09:00 – 10:30 Session 3: Remote Sensing and Landscape Archaeology

- **Lambers, Karsten:** Current Trends in Archaeological Object Detection in Remote Sensing Data.
- **Vermeulen, Frank; Verhoeven, Geert:** Aerial photography meets geophysics. Mapping the hilltop settlement of Montarice (Italy) by a multi-dimensional analysis of remote sensing imagery.
- **Gheyle, Wouter; Van den Berghe, Hanne; Stichelbaut, Birger; Saey, Timothy; Note, Nicolas; Hanssens, Daan; Van Meirvenne, Marc; Van Eetvelde, Veerle; Bourgeois, Jean:** Confronting past and present: the World War I conflict landscape in Belgium and Airborne Laser Scanning.

10:30 – 11:00 Coffee Break

11:00 – 12:30 Session 3: Remote Sensing and Landscape Archaeology

- **Goossens, Lise; Pilz, Dana; Meyer, Cornelius:** Bingo? Geophysical prospection and archaeological excavation of a Chalcolithic necropolis near Cabra (Andalusia, Spain).
- **De Smedt, Philippe:** Geophysical prospecting for site evaluation: ready meal or food for thought?
- **Verdonck, Lieven; Launaro, Alessandro; Millett, Martin; Vermeulen, Frank:** Georadar survey of two Roman towns in Lazio (Italy).

12:30 – 13:30 Lunch

13:30 – 15:00 Session 3: Remote Sensing and Landscape Archaeology

- **Swieder, Anna:** Bringing light into the dark forest. Using LiDAR for analysing a medieval and early modern landscape in the Harz Mountains, Central Germany.
- **Garcia-Sanchez, Jesús; Fontana, Giacomo:** In search of Montagna di Gildone: Developing an optimal workflow for the application of Lidar in central Italy.
- **Verhagen, Philip; Nuninger, Laure:** Integrating detection and modelling of ancient pathways: towards a spatio-temporal, multiscalar approach.

15:00 – 15:30 Coffee Break

15:30 – 17:00 Session 4: Digital Archaeology and the Wider Public

- **Langner, Martin; Zeckey, Alexander:** Collections of Classical Antiquities and Oculus Rift. A late baroque sculpture gallery as a case study.
- **Johnson, Paul:** Disseminating Data: utilising digital technology to make the invisible visible.
- **Lennart, Linde:** Gamification as a gateway?! Why archaeology should enter and engage with the virtual realm

17:00 Meeting Closure